

Linear Regressions of Predicting Rainfall over Kalay Region

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A wide range of rainfall forecast methods are employed in weather forecasting at regional and national levels. Fundamentally, there are two approaches to predict rainfall. They are empirical and dynamical methods. The empirical approach is based on analysis of historical data of the weather and its relationship to a variety of atmospheric and oceanic variables over different parts of the world. The most widely use empirical approaches used for climate prediction are regression, artificial neural network, stochastic, fuzzy logic and group method of data handling. In dynamical approach, predictions are generated by physical models based on systems of equations that predict the evolution of the global climate system in response to initial atmospheric conditions. The dynamical approaches are implemented using numerical weather forecasting method [2].

In this paper, rainfall prediction model over Kalay region for 10 years is analyzed with the use of empirical statistical technique, Linear Regression. Kalay is situated at the western bank of MyitThar River in Sagaing Division, in the upper of Myanmar. Kalay township is located the north latitude of 23° 12' and the east longitude of 94° 19'. The length of township is 12 miles from east to west and the breadth of it is 72 miles from North to South. So, we also focus on water level of MyitThar river for 10 years and analyze with the use of Linear Regression.

II. SIMPLE LINEAR REGRESSION MODELS

Regression is a statistical empirical technique of data mining which has wide range of application in many fields like business, biological sciences and climate prediction. It is becoming a promising tool in the society. Regression in simple terms is defined as predicting one variable from

ABSTRACT

Regression analysis is a statistical technique for investigating the relationship between variables. In this paper, rainfall and water level prediction models are discussed with the use of empirical statistical technique, Simple Linear Regression and analyzed the development of the predictive power of Linear Regression model to forecast the predicting rainfall and water level over Kalay in Sagaing Region for 10 years (2008-2017). The data of the monthly rainfall and water level used in this study were obtained from Meteorology and Hydrology Department of Kalay, Myanmar. In July 2015, Kalay was affected by the floods. So the rainfall and water level are predicted for next five years in this paper.

KEYWORDS: empirical statistical technique, linear regression, predicting, rainfall, water level

I. INTRODUCTION

The accurate and timely prediction of rainfall is a challenging task. Rainfall information is important for food production plan, water resource management and all activity plans in the nature. The occurrence of prolonged dry period or heavy rain at the critical stages of the crop growth and development may lead to significant reduce crop yield. Myanmar is an agricultural country and its economy is largely based upon crop productivity. Thus rainfall prediction becomes a significant factor in agricultural countries like Myanmar.

The simple linear regression model is as follows.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i + \varepsilon_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

In this equation, Y is value of dependent variable or say predicted variable, β_0 is constant value and β_1 is the predictor coefficient, the slope of regression line how much Y changes for one unit change in X, x_i are predictor variables or independent variables explaining the value of Y and ε is an error term. As the number of dependent variable increases the accuracy in predicted value also increases.

The estimated regression line or least squares regression line is

$$\hat{Y} = \hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1 x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where

$$\hat{\beta}_1 = \frac{S_{xy}}{S_{xx}}, \text{ is regression coefficient and}$$

$$\hat{\beta}_0 = \bar{y} - \hat{\beta}_1 \bar{x}.$$

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum x_i,$$

$$S_{xx} = \sum x_i^2 - n\bar{x}^2$$

$$S_{yy} = \sum y_i^2 - n\bar{y}^2$$

$$S_{xy} = \sum x_i y_i - n\bar{x}\bar{y}, \text{ is sample covariance.}$$

The residual; $e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$ and the following relations can easily be derived.

SST (Total sum of square) = SSR (Regression sum of square) + SSE (Error sum of square) where

$$SST = \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2 = S_{yy},$$

$$SSE = SST(1 - R^2).$$

The square of the sample correlation coefficient

$$r = \frac{S_{xy}}{\sqrt{S_{xx}\sqrt{S_{yy}}}}$$

Is called the coefficient of determination, R^2 . It plays an important role in model checking. It tells us the goodness of fit of the model [4], [5].

III. CASE STUDY

A. Rainfall of Kalay Region

A1: Mean Rainfall of Kalay Region for 10 years (2008-2017)

Table 1 shows the mean rainfall of Kalay Region for 10 years from 2008 to 2017.

Table1. Mean Rainfall & Estimated Mean Rainfall

No. of year X	No. of year	Mean rainfall Y	Estimated mean rainfall	Residual
1	2008	6.79	5.63	1.16
2	2009	5.14	5.62	-0.48
3	2010	5.01	5.61	-0.6
4	2011	6.2	5.61	0.59
5	2012	4.18	5.6	-1.42
6	2013	6.21	5.6	0.61
7	2014	4.63	5.59	-0.96
8	2015	6.4	5.58	0.82
9	2016	5.53	5.58	-0.05
10	2017	5.9	5.57	0.33

Simple Linear Regression Model for Mean Rainfall

Consider mean rainfall of Kalay Region for 10 years as shown in Table 1 and plot the scatter diagram shown in Figure 1a and 1b where number of years is represented along X-axis and mean rainfall of each year is represented along Y-axis.

According to above data, regression coefficient can be determined as follows. Here regression coefficient $\hat{\beta}_1$ is -0.0061 and $\hat{\beta}_0$ is 5.6327 . Therefore estimated regression model is $\hat{Y} = 5.6327 - 0.0061x$ and which is expressed in Figure 1a. Here, $R^2 = 0.0005$.

The interpretation of $\hat{\beta}_1 = -0.0061$ is that the mean rainfall expected to decrease, since the slope is negative.

Figure1b. Regression Line for Estimated Mean Rainfall

A2: Mean Rainfall in Rainy Season for 10years (2008-2017)

Table 2 shows the mean rainfall of rainy season in Kalay Region for 10 years from 2008 to 2017.

Table 2 Mean Rainfall of Rainy Season

No of Year	X	Y
16.64	1	2008
10.76	2	2009
10.28	3	2010
14.28	4	2011
10.56	5	2012
14.15	6	2013
11.15	7	2014
14.99	8	2015
12.32	9	2016
13.68	10	2017

Simple Linear Regression Model for Mean Rainfall in Rainy Season

According to above data, regression coefficient can be determined as follows. Here regression coefficient $\hat{\beta}_1$ is 0.0123 and $\hat{\beta}_0$ is 12.813 . Therefore estimated regression model is $\hat{Y} = 12.813 + 0.0123x$ and which is expressed in Figure 2. Here $R^2 = 0.0003$. The mean rainfall of Kalay region in rainy season can be expected to increase since the slope $\hat{\beta}_1 = 0.0123$ is positive.

Figure2. Estimated Regression Line for Mean Rainfall in

B. Water Level of MyitThar River

B1: Mean Highest Water Level of MyitThar River for 10 years (2008-2017)

Table 3 shows the mean highest water level of Mithras River for 10 years from 2008 to 2017.

Table 3 Mean Highest Water Level

No of Year	X	Y
527.5	1	2008
499	2	2009
471.7	3	2010
552.8	4	2011
419.2	5	2012
554.7	6	2013
426.4	7	2014
706.9	8	2015
600.8	9	2016
578.6	10	2017

Simple Linear Regression Model for Highest Water Level

Consider mean highest water level of MyitThar River for 10 years and plot the scatter diagram shown in Figure 3 where number of years is represented along X-axis and mean highest water level of each year is represented along Y-axis. Here regression coefficient $\hat{\beta}_1$ is 12.759 and $\hat{\beta}_0$ is 463.57. Therefore estimated regression model is $\hat{Y} = 463.57 + 12.759x$ and which is expressed in Figure 3. Here, $R^2 = 0.2003$. The mean highest water level of MyitThar river for 10 years can be expected to increase since the slope $\hat{\beta}_1 = 12.759$ is positive.

Figure 3. Estimated Regression Line for Mean Highest Water Level of Mithras River

B2: Mean Highest Water Level of Mithras River in Rainy Season

Table 4 shows the mean highest water level of Mithras River in rainy season, from Jun to September, for 10 years from 2008 to 2017.

Table 4. Mean Highest Water Level in Rainy Season

No of Year	X	Y
845.5	1	2008
623	2	2009
632.5	3	2010
902.25	4	2011
633.25	5	2012
868.75	6	2013
650.25	7	2014
1243.75	8	2015
783.25	9	2016
878	10	2017

Simple Linear Regression Model for Mean Highest Water Level in Rainy Season

According to above data, regression coefficient can be determined as follows. Here regression coefficient $\hat{\beta}_1$ is 24.194 and $\hat{\beta}_0$ is 673.58. Therefore estimated regression model is $\hat{Y} = 673.58 + 24.194x$ and which is expressed in Figure 4. Here, $R^2 = 0.1465$. The mean highest water level of MyitThar river in rainy season can be expected to increase since the slope $\hat{\beta}_1 = 24.194$ is positive.

Figure 4 Estimated Regression Line for Mean Highest Water Level in Rainy Season

C: Rainfall of Kalay Region and Highest Water Level of Mithras River

Table 5 shows the rainfall of Kalay region and highest water level of MyitThar river in July for 10 years from 2008 to 2017.

Table 5. Rainfall of Kalay Region and Highest Water Level of Mithras River in July

No. of year	Rain-fall	Highest water level	No. of year	Rain-fall	High-est water level		
1	2008	27.91	1024	6	2013	15.91	663
2	2009	8.39	442	7	2014	13.34	547
3	2010	9.18	609	8	2015	31.61	1942
4	2011	15.52	912	9	2016	16.64	691
5	2012	11.57	416	10	2017	17.08	866

The rainfall of Kalay region and highest water level of Mithras River in July for 10 years are analyzed as shown in Figures 5a and 5b respectively. We can obviously see that among them, in year 2015, both the rainfall and water level are maximum and

Figure 5a. Rainfall of Kalay Region in July

Figure 5b Highest Water Level of Mithras river in July

Figure 5c Highest Water Level and Danger Level of Mithras River in July

Table 6. Rainfall and Highest Water Level in 2008 and 2015

		2008	2015
Rainfall	in July	27.91	31.61
	in rainy season (mean)	16.64	14.99
	for a year (mean)	6.79	6.4
Highest Water Level	in July	1024	1942
	in rainy season (mean)	845.5	1243.75
	for a year (mean)	527.5	706.92

According to the previous data analysis and trends of regression lines, we can forecast for the estimated mean rainfall of Kalay region and mean highest water level of MyitThar river for next 5 years from 2018 to 2022 as shown in Table 7.

Table 7 Estimated Rainfall and Highest Water Level in next 5 years (from 2018 to 2022)

		Rainfall		Highest water level	
		in rainy season (Mean)	For a year (Mean)	in rainy season (Mean)	for a year (Mean)
1	2018	12.9483	5.5656	939.714	603.919
2	2019	12.9606	5.5595	963.908	616.678
3	2020	12.9729	5.5534	988.102	629.437
4	2021	12.9852	5.5473	1012.3	642.196
5	2022	12.9975	5.5412	1036.49	654.955

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In years 2008 and 2015, the mean rainfall of Kalay Region is maximum based on previous 10 years data and it will be expected to decrease since the slope of the regression line is negative. Furthermore, in those years, the mean rainfall of Kalay Region in rainy season is also maximum but it will be expected to increase since the slope of the regression line is positive.

Similarly, in year 2015, the mean highest water level of MyitThar river is maximum based on previous 10 years data and it will be expected to increase since the slope of the regression lines are positive, so does the mean highest water level of MyitThar river in rainy season.

In July 2015, a monsoon rain triggered a natural disaster, and a state of emergency was declared in four regions of the country. The disaster caused a flash flood in Kalay and surrounding areas. Kalay was devastated by the disaster. The reason is because of the maximum rainfall and water level of MyitThar river. In July 2015, both the rainfall and water level are maximum and these are above the danger level 1100cm. According to data analysis for next 5 years, the rainfall will be maximum and water level can be reached to the danger level. So preparations will be needed to prevent from flash flood in Kalay and surrounding areas.

V. CONCLUSION

The values of rainfall are calculated using the data collected over ten years. Mean rainfall of Kalay region and highest water level of MyitThar river for 10 years and rainy season as well are used as a dependent variables in simple linear regression, which can improve the efficiency of prediction of rainfall and water level.

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REFERENCES

- [1] MAINavid and NH Niloy, "Multiple Linear Regressions for Predicting Rainfall for Bangladesh." *Communications, Science PG*, vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 1-4,1990
- [2] Wint Thida Zaw and Thinn Thu Naing, "Empirical Statistical Modeling of Rainfall Prediction over Myanmar." *International Journal of Computer and Information Engineering*, vol. 2, No. 10, pp. 3418-3421, 2008
- [3] Paras and Sanjay Mathur, "A Simple Weather Forecasting Model using Mathematical Regression." *Indian Research Journal of Extension Education, Special Issue*, vol. 1, pp. 161-168, 2012
- [4] Douglas C. Montgomery, Elizabeth A. Peck and G. Geoffrey Vining, "Introduction to Linear Regression Analysis." Fifth Edition, Wiley Series in Probability and Statistics,2012
- [5] John O. Rawlings, Sastry G. Pantula and David A. Dickey, "Applied Regression Analysis." Second Edition, Springer, 1998

